

Neural Network-Based Control of TDFAs

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Abstract— **The complexity of controlling optical amplifiers with multiple pumps, like Thulium-Doped Fiber Amplifiers (TDFAs), stems from the need to select the optimal pumping to ensure proper operation (e.g., maintaining a constant target output power). Therefore, an experimental demonstration of neural network-assisted SDN control of TDFAs configuration is presented. The proposed optimization enables efficient automated TDFAs control, resulting in an RMSE of 0.23 dBm between target and actual output power.**

Keywords—*Multi-band, TDFAs, SDN control, neural networks, NETCONF, YANG*

I. INTRODUCTION

Multi-Band (MB) optical networks have been driven by the need to increase the capacity of currently deployed optical networks (i.e., C-band and more recently C+L [1]), while postponing the installation of the new fibers [2]. However, MB optical networks face several technical challenges, such as introducing new components and optimizing network performance while accounting for wideband impairments like stimulated Raman scattering (SRS) [3].

The availability of amplification technologies plays a key role in enabling the MB. Two architectural approaches are accordingly discussed in [4]: (1) optical bands are demultiplexed, guided to their dedicated amplifiers, and then re-multiplexed; and (2) the adoption of MB optical components, such as optical amplifiers and wavelength selective switches (WSSs) operating in more than one band. However, a significant issue of the latter approach is the absence of a single Rare-Earth Doped Fiber for amplification across multiple bands [4, 5]. Thulium-Doped Fiber Amplifiers (TDFAs), sufficiently developed for commercial use [6], are suitable for the S-band. Moreover, S-band WSSs are also commercially available [7], suggesting that S-band use could be the next step toward broader spectrum utilization.

The change in the underlying infrastructure (i.e., amplifiers operating beyond C and L) demands a control plane that can manage amplifiers with different configuration properties. In the context of Software-Defined Networking (SDN), we have

proposed a YANG model for optical amplifiers operating in MB optical networks [8], enabling the SDN control through NETCONF protocol. However, the operation of optical amplifiers (e.g., TDFAs) is characterized by nonlinear behavior, dependent on parameters such as pumping currents, pumping wavelengths, input signal power, and operating spectral range [9, 10]. Therefore, modeling amplifier physics is critical for configuring and optimizing overall system. Traditionally, analytical models have been employed for such tasks, however, optimizing optical amplifiers with multiple pumps (e.g., three pumps for TDFAs) is challenging due to complex nonlinear equations describing pumping, signal, and noise interactions. In contrast, machine learning (ML) may play an important role in the complex modeling and configuration of amplifier operations, effectively overcoming the complexity that would otherwise be managed through alternative implementations (e.g., look-up tables, analytical models, manual configurations, etc.). In fact, many studies on ML-based modeling of the EDFAs and Raman amplifiers have been conducted, addressing the issues of predicting the amplifier gain or pump powers, especially when multiple pumps are employed [9-11]. However, the application of such techniques for TDFAs optimization has not been explored.

The focus of this work is to implement neural network (NN) – based SDN control of TDFAs. The adopted TDFAs employ three pumps to enable the proper operation (which is in power mode [6], i.e. constant target output power). Nevertheless, the main challenge is selecting, thus configuring, the appropriate pumping currents that result in the desired output power. In this paper, a NN predicts pumps configuration to achieve the target optical power. The experimental demonstration of the NN capable of learning the relationship between wavelength, input power, target output power, and the corresponding TDFAs pumping currents is presented. The results suggest reliable TDFAs operation, with RMSE of 0.23 dBm in the desired output.

II. NEURAL NETWORK-BASED MODELING

This section describes the adopted NN model and the experimental setup for collecting data for NN training: the TDFAs output power based on signal wavelength, input power, and pumping configuration. Optical signals operating in the S-band pass a variable optical attenuator (VOA) that allowed total input power adjustment in the range from -35 dBm to -5 dBm, used with a granularity of 5 dBm. The adopted TDFAs allows

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the monitoring of input power, pumping current values (main pump, and two sub-pumps), and output power. Its operational spectrum spans from 1470 to 1520 nm, but due to the limitations of the adopted tunable S-band source, data collection covers the range from 1490 to 1520 nm in 5 nm increments. The main pump is set to operate in a constant output power mode, although this power level varies with changes in input power. Therefore, by adjusting the pumping currents of the other two pumps, the power can be adjusted to reach the desired target level. Pump two is incremented in 70 mA steps up to 560 mA, while pump three varies up to 190 mA in 10 mA steps. For each combination of wavelength, input power, and pumping currents, the TDFA output power is collected, resulting in a dataset of 6273 data entries. After normalization and shuffling, the dataset is divided into three sets: 80% for training, 10% for validation, and the remaining 10% for testing.

Fig. 1. Neural Network Architecture

The NN-based approach focuses on addressing an inverse problem, which involves predicting the appropriate pumping configuration to achieve the target output power, considering the operational wavelength and input power. The choice of a proper NN architecture strongly depends on amplifier being modeled [11]. Therefore, adapting the NN to the unique characteristics of the amplifier is essential for attaining high accuracy and low complexity. The proposed model takes the signal wavelength, input power, and the target output power as input parameters (as seen in Fig. 1). The NN output provides the associated pumping currents necessary to achieve the desired optical power. The architecture comprises three hidden layers, each containing 100 nodes and utilizes a Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function. The training process employs a stochastic gradient descent optimization algorithm (Adam) and the Mean Squared Error (MSE) as a cost function, enabling the model to learn the accurate mapping between input and output parameters. Finally, the trained model is utilized by the SDN controller to push the proper configuration via NETCONF protocol.

III. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION AND RESULTS

This section details the demonstration and performance analysis of the proposed model. After analysis, the model is deployed and run at a custom-built SDN controller. The trained NN model learns the relationship between the pumping currents and the desired output power, input power, and wavelength.

Fig. 2. Training and Validation Learning Curves with the MSE of Normalized Pumping Values

The learning curve depicted in Fig. 2. illustrates a strong alignment between the performance of the model and the training dataset, indicating that the model fits the provided data effectively and exhibits a reliable ability to generalize to unseen examples.

The Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), which quantifies the average difference between predicted and measured pumping values, is used to characterize prediction accuracy. While the RMSE values for pump two and pump three predictions are 138.86 mA and 22.77 mA, respectively, and might suggest suboptimal performance, other aspects should be considered to determine the capability of the NN model to reach the target output power. In fact, multiple different combinations of pump values that lead to the same output power have been identified through experimental measurements, demonstrating the intrinsic redundancy of the TDFA. For example, by configuring pump two and pump three to 470 mA and 70 mA, or 353 mA and 130 mA, respectively, the output power of 13.5 dBm is achieved. Hence, to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the model's performance, it is essential to validate the test dataset on the actual device.

The experimental validation of the NN model is performed

Fig. 3. Normalized Frequency Density of Error Distribution

TABLE I. SDN (RE-)CONFIGURATION OF PUMPS FOR TARGET OUTPUT POWER OF 10 DBM ACCORDING TO THE SCENARIO

scenario	condition	in [dBm]	w1 [nm]	p2 [mA]	p3 [mA]
wavelength reconfiguration	initial	-16.56	1495	270	120
	reconfiguration	-16.72	1520	300	144
input power change	initial	-11.6	1510	280	106
	reconfiguration	-16.64	1510	327	152

using the same setup as described in the previous section. The NN model generated predictions for the required pumping currents based on a specific target output power, wavelength, and input power. Subsequently, the TDFA was configured according to the predicted pumping values, and the actual output power was measured and collected. The RMSE between the target and actual output power values is 0.23 dBm, with the maximum error being 1.44 dBm. Fig. 3 shows the Normalized Frequency Density (NFD) of error distribution. It is important to note that larger deviations between the target output power and actual values, particularly outliers showing errors of 1.2 dBm and 1.44 dBm (as seen in Fig. 3.), are associated with the data points corresponding to the minimum and maximum target output power values. This observation suggests that incorporating additional training data, particularly addressing the endpoints of the target output power range, may improve prediction accuracy. The NN-based approach yields a reliable operation of the TDFA (i.e., target output power) based on the prediction of the appropriate pumping configuration. Furthermore, simplifying the selection of pumping currents for efficient control enables to quickly adjust the amplifier parameters in dynamic network conditions (e.g., network failures). Table 1 presents the pumping (re-)configuration values required to achieve 10 dBm at the output under two different scenarios: wavelength reconfiguration or change in input power (e.g., due to the unexpected loss). For example, to achieve the target output power of 10 dBm at 1510 nm with the input power of -11.6 dBm, pump two and pump three should initially be configured to 280 mA and 106 mA, respectively. However, as the input power drops to -16.64 dBm, the SDN controller reacts accordingly by utilizing the NN model for pump prediction based on the new input power. Finally, it sends

```
<multiband-optical-amplifiers xmlns="http://openconfig.net/yang/optical-amplifier">
  <optical-amplifier>
    <amplifier>
      <id>1</id>
      <config>
        <id>1</id>
        <name>TDFA</name>
        <amp-mode>CONSTANT_POWER</amp-mode>
        <target-output-power>10.0</target-output-power>
        <active>true</active>
        <laser-diode-pumps>
          <pump-ID>
            <pump-id>2</pump-id>
            <pump-bias-current>327.0</pump-bias-current>
          </pump-ID>
          <pump-ID>
            <pump-id>3</pump-id>
            <pump-bias-current>152.0</pump-bias-current>
          </pump-ID>
        </laser-diode-pumps>
      </config>
    </amplifier>
  </optical-amplifier>
</multiband-optical-amplifiers>
```

Fig. 4. NETCONF <edit-config> Message

the <edit-config> NETCONF message (Fig. 4) to the TDFA, relying on the YANG model proposed in [8], thus reconfiguring pumps to 327 mA and 152 mA. This adaptive response ensures that quality of transmission is guaranteed, which is a critical aspect in optical networks.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper we propose and experimentally demonstrate NN-based control of the TDFA, employing three laser diodes pumps. From the SDN control perspective, the main challenge is selecting the appropriate pumping currents that result in the desired output power. The proposed NN model, trained using experimental measurements, aims at optimizing the pumping configuration of the employed TDFA, by learning the mapping between target output power, input power, and wavelength and appropriate pump values. The RMSE between the target and actual output power values is 0.23 dBm, demonstrating reliable performance.

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